

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

YEAR: 2024

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL

ISSN: 3048-7951

A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER-REVIEWED
& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

Google Scholar

This is to certify that the research paper entitled “Agricultural skill development among youth: a prospect for sustainable growth”, authored by “Dr. Netramani Pradhan”, has been successfully published in ADEJ, Volume – 3, Issue – 2 (April-June 2026).

The paper has been assigned the DOI link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20496276>

The manuscript is plagiarism-free and has undergone a rigorous double-blind peer review process, ensuring standards of originality, quality, and academic integrity as evaluated by the Review Committee of ADEJ.

Editor-in-Chief
AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL
(ISSN: 3048-7951)
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India

www.educarepublication.com

adeduxian@gmail.com

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Mrs. JYOTISHA PANDEY
Managing Director
AD EDUXIAN PUBLICATION
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India